

Redox-mediated hybrid zinc-air flow batteries for more resilient integrated power systems - Grant Agreement Number 101115535

Deliverable D1.5 – Data Management Plan

Dissemination level

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SEN – Sensitive; only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	6
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose of DMP	7
1.2 Relationship to other deliverables	7
2 ReZilient data	7
2.1 Data type, format, and size	9
2.2 Background data	9
2.3 ReZilient data storage platforms	9
2.4 Instructions and process diagram for data handling in ReZilient.....	10
3 FAIR data management	12
3.1 Making data findable	12
3.2 Making data accessible	13
3.3 Making data interoperable.....	14
3.4 Making data reusable.....	14
4 Data Security	15
4.1 Active Project - Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint	15
4.2 Repository - Data security as specified for Zenodo.....	16
5 Ethical Aspects	16
6 Contact information	18
7 References	18
List of Figures	19

List of Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations

Term	Explanation
BibTeX	A reference management software for formatting lists of references.
CC licence	Creative Commons licenses are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. ¹
CC BY	This CC-license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, if they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.
CC0	CC0 enables scientists, educators, artists and other creators and owners of copyright- or database-protected content to waive those interests in their works and thereby place them as completely as possible in the public domain, so that others may freely build upon, enhance, and reuse the works for any purposes without restriction under copyright or database rights.
CC BY-NC	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, and although their new work must also acknowledge you and be non-commercial, they don't have to license their derivative works on the same terms.
CC BY-SA	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, if they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to "copyleft" free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use.
CSL	Citation Style Language An open XML-based standard to format citations and bibliographies.
Deliverable type	R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports) DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. OTHER: Software, technical diagram
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable data
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation. Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
GitLab	GitLab is a platform for collaborative software development, offering Git repository management, issue tracking, CI/CD pipelines (Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment/Delivery), and collaboration tools. It simplifies project management by providing a centralized hub for code hosting, issue tracking, and automated workflows. It supports in efficiently developing, testing, and deploying software while facilitating communication and collaboration among team members.
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation An open-standard file format.
MARXML	An XML schema based on the common MARC21 standards
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.

¹ Creative Commons homepage: <https://creativecommons.org/>

Term	Explanation
Research data	Refers to information, facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, and images.
REST API	REST is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating web services. API stands for Application Programming Interface
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security These are protocols offering secure communication on the internet.
Zenodo	Zenodo is a catch-all research data repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share research results, make research results citable, and search and reuse open research results from other projects. Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal and hosted by the CERN cloud infrastructure.

Executive Summary

The purpose of ReZilient Deliverable 1.3 Data Management Plan (DMP) is to contribute to good data handling by describing what research data the project expects to use, data handling principles, and an assessment of what data can be shared with the public or why data cannot be open. Furthermore, it gives instructions on naming conventions and metadata structure.

Ethical aspects related to data collection, generation and sharing have been considered. All datasets will be uploaded, stored and handled in accordance with national and European rules on data protection and privacy. Metadata will be added to all datasets, and instructions on how to upload, store, publish and preserve research data is provided in this document.

ReZilient will use Zenodo, a trusted and OpenAire compliant data repository to comply with the FAIR data principles. The ReZilient project will also use GitLab, a trusted platform for collaborative software development, to comply with the Horizon Europe Open Access mandate². All data sets with dissemination level "Public" will be uploaded to the ReZilient communities hosted on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/rezilient-project-eu>) and GitLab (<https://gitlab.sintef.no/rezilient>).

Each dataset will be given a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI), supplied with relevant metadata, and linked to the project acronym and grant agreement number. Publications and underlying research data will be linked, and a Creative Commons license will regulate reuse of the ReZilient research data. Data security arrangements are defined.

The DMP will be updated in project months 30 and 48. The final version of the DMP will include instructions for how to access and reuse open research data from ReZilient.

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/open-access_en

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of DMP

The DMP provides an overview of research data the project is expected to generate or reuse, the types and formats of this data, and how this data is processed and stored to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling during the project's lifetime, and to describe how the research data will be curated and preserved.

The online tool DMPOnline, hosted by Data Curation Centre, has been used to generate content for this document³. The tool is based on the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#) and guidelines for FAIR data.

In ReZilient:

- Project participants who are responsible for, or in any way involved with, data collection and data handling can use this document for instructions on how to handle, store and process data.
- All project participants can use this document to get an overview of data collected in the project and how this is processed, stored and made accessible.

External audience:

- The **Data Summary** and **FAIR Data Management** sections can be used by all relevant stakeholders who are interested in ReZilient related activities and research topics to get an overview of the data collected in the project, how to access this data, and, if applicable, how to re-use this data in their own activities.

1.2 Relationship to other deliverables

The ReZilient DMP will be updated in D1.6 RP2 update of the Data Management Plan due month 30, and the final version due month 48 will be presented in D1.7 RP3 update of the Data Management Plan.

Deliverable D1.2 Project Management Handbook describes the internal ReZilient Sharepoint structure and the internal data reporting tool that is used for internally managing the datasets from ReZilient, as well as the reporting of datasets to the funding agency.

2 ReZilient data

The overall motivation for data collection in ReZilient is to:

- Facilitate evaluations and learning
- Evaluating results/tech/solutions
- Validating results/tech/solution
- Gathering feedback to improve results/tech/solution

Only data that is needed to perform project activities will be collected, and as far as possible, participants will not be asked to provide personal data unless this is necessary. Table 2 provides a list of all types of data currently expected to be generated in ReZilient and their planned accessibility. We recognise that this list will develop and grow as the project evolves.

³ https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/about_us

Table 2: Expected data in ReZn ilient with access level

WP, task	Type of dataset	Description/purpose	File format	Responsible partner	Origin	Access level	Order of size of dataset
2.1	Microscopy pictures	Analyse morphology	.gif/.jpeg	TUD	Taken from partners	Confidential	
2.2	composition data and stability of coating	Analyse protective coating	.xlsx/word	TUD	Measured at TUDelft	Confidential	
2.3	Impedance data of Zn/ZnO electrode	Analyse charge transfer of electrons and ions	.xlsx	TUD	Simulation data	Confidential	
3.1	table of organic compounds	verifying optimal mediators	NA	TUD	TUD	Confidential	NA
3.1	table of organic compounds	discovery of new mediators	NA	AU	AU	Confidential	NA
3.2	table of potential catalysts	optimisation of catalysts	.xlsx/word	TUD	TUD	Confidential	NA
3.2	table of inorganic compounds	testing of catalyst for mediated ORR and OER	NA	AU	AU	Confidential	NA
3.3	standard battery testing data (V-cap, cap - cycle # etc)	proof-of-concept mediated cycling of Zn/ZnO	NA	AU	AU	Confidential	NA
4.1	results from MD simulations giving fluid properties and transport numbers	Input to open-source model for battery components, input to experiments	.csv	SINTEF	Simulation data	open access	
4.2	Results from Lattice Boltzmann modelling of semi solid electrode (particle size distribution, viscosity, etc.)	Input to open-source model for battery components, experimntal validation of models	.csv	TUD	Simulation data	Open access	
4.3	Results from pore network modelling of porous solid electrode (permeability, surface area, etc.)	Input to open-source model for battery components	.csv	SINTEF	Simulation data	Open access	
4.4	Software	Implementation of models for flow battery components	.py (mainly)	SINTEF		Open source	
4.4	Results from open-source model for flow battery components (polarization curves etc.)	Validate model against experiments	.csv	SINTEF	Simulation data	Open access	
5.4	standard battery testing data (V-cap, cap - cycle # etc)	Demonstration of concept	NA	AU	AU	Confidential	NA
6.1	NA	Supply, transportation, demand, and storage	NA	SINTEF	Collected from partners	Confidential	kB
6.2	to be determined later		.csv/.xlsx	VBP			
6.3	Synthesis and manufacturing data (energy + materials, e.g. bill of materials); performance data (losses, expected lifetime)	Input to life cycle assessment (can rely on inputs from WP5, WP3, and WP2)	NA	SINTEF	Measured/expert opinion	Confidential	NA
6.4	to be determined later			VBP			
7.2	Roadmap, reports, technical data	Material to support preparation of the portfolio roadmap	.docx/.pdf/.xlsx/	SINTEF	Collected from Portfolio partners	Confidential	NA
7.4	Project communication material	Material to support workshops, project meetings, summer schools	.docx/.pptx/.xlsx/	SINTEF	Collected from Portfolio partners	Confidential	NA
7.5	List of Key Performance Indicators	Technical data to support techno-economic benchmarking	.docx/.pdf/.xlsx/	SINTEF	Collected from Portfolio partners	Confidential	NA

2.1 Data type, format, and size

ReZilient will collect, generate and reuse various types of data, such as:

- Observations and collected data
 - Experimental data
 - Survey/interview/transcript data
- Calculation data (data from models, simulations, and other calculations)
- Experimental data (results from controlled trials or test data)
- Raw and processed data
- Measuring sequences, code
- Algorithms, scripts
- Audio-visual data
- Physical objects (samples, demos)

Data will be organised in datasets according to type, content or origin of the data.

ReZilient will aim at using widely accepted formats for data generation, such as:

- Documents/Reports/Publications: .PDF/A, txt, doc/docx
- Spreadsheets: .xls/.xlsx
- Databases: .csv
- Audio files: .mp3, .wav, .wma, .ra
- Pictures: jpg, png
- Video: avi, flv, mov, mp4, wmv

The estimated size of the data is given in Table 2.

2.2 Background data

"Background" means any data, including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is:

- held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the agreement and
- needed to implement the action or exploit the results

ReZilient background is defined for each partner in the ReZilient Consortium Agreement.

2.3 ReZilient data storage platforms

2.3.1 SINTEF SharePoint

All datasets in ReZilient will be stored in a SINTEF SharePoint project site. This will be the project's online working and collaboration area while the project is active.

All partners will be responsible for uploading datasets they have collected/generated during the project. Each dataset will be catalogued in [ReZilient Datasets overview.xlsx](#) providing an overview of all datasets in the project, as well as uploaded to [09 Datasets](#), a dedicated research data folder in the SharePoint site. All datasets will use standard SharePoint version control, and access control is available to enable limited access to certain types of data.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- Project ID (Grant No)
- Data Owner
- File name
- Version
- WP number
- File type
- Date/time
- Dissemination level
- Keyword(s)

2.3.2 ReZilient code repositories on GitLab

To share battery modelling codes developed in the project, a ReZilient project page and associated repositories will be hosted on GitLab (<https://gitlab.sintef.no/rezilient>). The ReZilient project will use GitLab to comply with the Horizon Europe Open Access mandate⁴. All data sets with dissemination level "Public" will be uploaded to the ReZilient community in GitLab. GitLab and Zenodo offer easy coupling of code repositories to datasets as well as the generation of DOIs to make the code citable. Scientific publications derived from the modelling codes and underlying datasets will be made open accessible and linked via the Zenodo page.

2.3.3 Zenodo Data Repository

ReZilient will use Zenodo, a trusted and OpenAire compliant repository to comply with the FAIR principles. All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the ReZilient Community in the repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/rezilient-project-eu>). In addition, the project can choose to upload other datasets (not directly linked to publications and deliverables) with dissemination level "Public" and make them openly accessible via the repository.

2.4 Instructions and process diagram for data handling in ReZilient

Figure 1: Data handling procedures for ReZilient. SP=ReZilient Sharepoint.

⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/open-access_en

Table 3 and Figure 1 provide instructions to project participants on how to upload datasets and outcomes from the data to SharePoint and the Zenodo.

Table 3: Instructions for uploading datasets to SharePoint

Upload instructions – ReZilient Sharepoint Site
<p>Please upload all ReZilient data sets to this folder in the ReZilient Sharepoint site: 09 Datasets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use this naming convention (for details see 2.1.5):<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ <i>Descriptive text ReZilient_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber</i>○ <i>Descriptive text ReZilient_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber</i>• Be sure to use the same file name when uploading later versions• Add mandatory metadata in this list/workbook/database: ReZilient Datasets overview.xlsx
Upload instructions – GitLab Repository
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Battery modelling codes developed in the project will be stored in a ReZilient project page and associated repositories, hosted on GitLab (https://gitlab.sintef.no/rezilient). To do this you must complete the following steps:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Set up Git (Install Git on your computer https://git-scm.com/downloads and configure Git with your name and email)○ Request invitation to the ReZilient repository (WP4 “Modelling” Leader)○ Clone the GitLab repository to your local machine○ Add files and commit changes (with a descriptive commit message)○ Push the committed changes to the GitLab repository
Upload instructions – Zenodo Data Repository
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as “Public” should, in addition, be uploaded to Zenodo. To do this you must complete the following steps:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Create a profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files○ Click on the <i>ReZilient Community</i> link above, or search for “<i>ReZilient Community</i>” under the “Communities” tab at the top of the Zenodo site https://zenodo.org/communities/rezilient-project-eu○ On the Community site, click the green “New upload” button in the top right corner○ Enter requested data and confirm the upload.○ Remember to add the European Commission community in the box labelled “communities”. You can use the search function to locate the community and add it. The data will then automatically be uploaded to both communities, so you don’t have to do it twice.• Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication or EC approval of deliverables for underlying datasets. Other datasets will be uploaded in the final month of the project at the latest.• Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets collected/generated by them.

3 FAIR data management

ReZilient will manage data in accordance with the principles of FAIR data management⁵ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data) The project aims to maximize access to, and re-use of research data generated by the project.

At the same time, there are potentially datasets, or parts of datasets, generated in this project that cannot be shared due to e.g.

- protection of results prior to commercial exploitation
- protection of business sensitive information

Table 2 provides a current overview of the expected types of data in ReZilient and their accessibility.

3.1 Making data findable

3.1.1 ReZilient Community in Zenodo and GitLab

ReZilient will use the Zenodo repository as the main tool to make our research data findable in accordance with the FAIR data principles.

A *ReZilient* community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/rezilient-project-eu>) has been established in the repository, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community. This will ensure harvesting of project results by OpenAire and provide maximum findability. All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number, Project Name and Acronym. The repository provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements.

Modelling code and/or software generated in the project will be hosted on GitLab (<https://gitlab.sintef.no/rezilient>), which is a widely used platform to share version-controlled open-source computer codes. GitLab is closely linked to Zenodo, which can provide DOIs to make code citable and provide links to associated publications and/or datasets.

3.1.2 Metadata in Zenodo

Metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default be as follows:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Version numbers
- Creator (Name and ORCID)
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

In addition, the project name and GA number should be added.

⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

3.1.3 Versioning and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

Zenodo provides DOI versioning of all datasets uploaded to their communities, which allows us to edit and update the uploaded datasets after they have been published. This also allows us to cite specific versions of an upload and cite all versions of an upload. Additionally, Zenodo can provide DOIs to make code on GitLab citable and provide links to associated publications and/or datasets.

3.1.4 Approach to search keywords

Each partner who collects and generates public datasets will be responsible for uploading these to the repository and to assign specific search keywords relevant for these datasets. Dataset specific keywords must be descriptive to the content of the dataset. In addition, the project has defined a set of general keywords that apply to all public datasets, scientific publications and public deliverables. These are as follows:

- Flow batteries
- Long duration energy storage (LDES)
- Zinc-air flow batteries

Naming conventions. Data will be named using the following naming conventions:

Descriptive text_ReZilient_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber

Descriptive text_ReZilient_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber

Explanation of the naming convention:

- "Descriptive text" refers to a *short* description of the content of the dataset (see example)
- "ReZilient" refers to the project's acronym
- "DeliverableNumber" refers to the deliverable number as described in the DoA
- "PublicationNumber" refers to the number the publication has in the project internal directory of all publications from the project
- "UniqueDataNumber" is the number automatically generated by the research metadata list in SharePoint

3.2 Making data accessible

The EU's Open Science Policy aims to make research data generated by Horizon Europe projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons.

All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning). Data sets with dissemination level "confidential" (non-anonymous datasets) will not be shared. Potentially, some datasets might be restricted due to protection for commercial exploitation. If such cases arise during the project, this will be stated in the final version of the DMP.

Metadata including licenses for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also

retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application. No specific software or hardware is needed to access and reuse the data.

Table 2 will compile a list of types of datasets expected to be generated in ReZilient and their planned accessibility. This list constitutes the first version of dataset description, and we recognise that it will develop and grow as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets currently remain unknown, e.g. size of the datasets. An updated version of the list containing all dataset details will be provided at the end of the project.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Zenodo uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite and export to Mendeley. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

3.4 Making data reusable

ReZilient will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) all public data sets, and regulate this by using Creative Commons Licences.

3.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences

ReZilient will use Creative Commons licences (CC), which are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC BY license will be applied for public ReZilient research data. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you. This does not preclude the use of less restrictive licenses as CC 0 or more restrictive licenses as CC BY-ND, which does not allow derivations.

Application of licences will be assessed on a case-by-basis in close collaboration with the Coordinator, Innovation Manager and partners concerned.

3.4.2 Availability and longevity of the PROJECT research data sets

Public (anonymous) data

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made available no later than by journal publication. The data will be linked to the publication. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved and accepted by the EC. For other public datasets not directly linked to a scientific publication or deliverable, such datasets will be made available upon assessment by the responsible partner that it is ready for publishing, and in the final month of the project at the latest.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licences. Data classified as confidential will not be reusable due to privacy/security concerns.

The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime stated by the host laboratory CERN. If Zenodo has to close their operations, they have provided a guarantee that they will migrate all content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories.

Confidential (non-anonymous) data

All non-anonymous data will be deleted at the end of the project. In case permission is given by the party providing and owning the data, some non-anonymous data will be kept for a maximum of 4 months after the contractual end date of the project⁶. The additional 4 months is to keep the underlying datasets available to allow the completion of any scientific publications being prepared towards the end of the project.

An exemption is pictures and videos, taken with consent from voluntary project/pilot/workshop/exercise participants, that are used for communication purposes. If consent is not withdrawn at an earlier time, such data will be kept for up to 4 years after the end of the project in order to comply with the EC contractual obligation to continue dissemination, communication and exploitation activities after the project ends. If a party withdraws the consent to use this material (pictures, videos), it will be deleted without delay.

4 Data Security

In this chapter, the security features of the research data infrastructure used to store and handle data in ReZilient are described.

4.1 Active Project - Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint

SINTEF Sharepoint is the online collaboration platform used in ReZilient. A dedicated project site has been established on this platform, accessible only by the partner representatives in the consortium. Furthermore, a dedicated folder for research datasets is set up, allowing for stricter access control than the main project site.

The ReZilient Sharepoint site has the following security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only). Further access restrictions on specific folders could if necessary be enabled.
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and the SINTEF SharePoint site.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents and/or registers possible manipulation of data.

Documents and elements in the SINTEF SharePoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions, based in Ireland and the Netherlands. There will be no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA and associated countries⁷.

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor. As a baseline, all project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF's ICT policy, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.

⁶ At present, the contractual end date of the ReZilient project is: 30.09.2027. However, changes can be made to this date during the project (e.g. in case of a project extension) and the final version of the DMP will provide the exact date.

⁷ EEA = Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein

4.2 Repository- Data security as specified for GitLab

The following list describes the security settings for GitLab:

- Versions: Data files are versioned. Every change made to the codebase or any other files is tracked, providing a detailed history of modifications. Users can easily revert to previous versions if needed, ensuring data integrity and traceability.
- Replicas: GitLab supports high availability and disaster recovery through various replication and backup mechanisms. Administrators can set up GitLab instances in a clustered configuration with multiple replicas to ensure redundancy and fault tolerance. Additionally, regular backups of data can be scheduled to prevent data loss in case of hardware failures or other disasters.
- Retention period: GitLab allows administrators to configure data retention policies to control how long data is kept within the system. This includes setting retention periods for backups, logs, and other data generated by the platform.
- Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

4.3 Repository- Data security as specified for Zenodo

The following list describes the security settings for Zenodo:

- Versions: Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and records are preserved.
- Replicas: All data files are stored in the CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- Retention period: Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. The host laboratory of Zenodo CERN, has defined a lifetime for the repository of the next 20 years minimum.
- Functional preservation: Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- File preservation: Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.
- Fixity and authenticity: All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content.
- Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, a guarantee has been made from Zenodo to migrate all content to suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

5 Ethical Aspects

The proposed work in ReZilient will fully comply with the regulations set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁸. In addition, ReZilient comply with the

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out.

The ReZilient partners are obliged by European and national law (GDPR) to protect personal data.

The coordinator of ReZilient, SINTEF, follow ethical guidelines in its work, and all work conducted by SINTEF is subject to the SINTEF Ethics Council and the appointed Ethics Representative. SINTEF will also ensure that all participants in ReZilient follow the ethical guidelines of SINTEF. Important aspects with respect to this are:

- The ethical guidelines are based on the vision of using science and technology to create a better society and are reviewed continuously to ensure they stay up to date with developments in society and the challenges of today. They generally fall into these categories: research ethics, business ethics, and ethics in interpersonal relationships.
- SINTEF is a member of the UN Global Compact and Transparency International, and SINTEF's ethics are guided by the principles highlighted by these organisations, as well as based on the regulations of the national ethics committees, the principles promoted by the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE), and on international conventions such as the Vancouver Convention. When dilemmas of research ethics require an assessment beyond the scope of our guidelines, our Ethics Council and Ethics Representative, we refer to statements from the EGE.
- All SINTEF's employees are expected to act in accordance with the ethical guidelines and principles. As coordinator of the PROJECT project, SINTEF will ensure that any ethical issues, which may arise, will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.
- SINTEF follows the Vancouver Recommendations for publication of scientific work.

Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

Currently, no ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data generation and sharing have been identified. Ethical and legal aspects related to research data generated by the project will be considered as the work proceeds.

ReZilient may collect pictures and videos for use in communication activities (website, newsletter, social media). Such data will only be collected with prior consent from the people involved and only used for as long as consent is given. Pictures and video can contain personal data if an individual is the focus of the image or video. Examples include: 1) pictures/video of individuals stored together with personal details (e.g. identity cards); 2) pictures/video of individuals posted on the project website along with biographical details; 3) individual images published in a newsletter. Examples of pictures and video that is unlikely to contain personal data are: 1) pictures/video where people are incidentally included in an image or are not the focus (e.g. at a big conference/workshop); 2) images of people who are no longer alive (the GDPR only applies to living people,).

When collecting pictures and videos, ReZilient will follow established guidance and best practice on collecting and processing such data to ensure that adherence to legal requirements. Under no circumstances will pictures containing personal information be publicly shared without the subject's explicit consent.

6 Contact information

Use of e-mail addresses in ReZilient SharePoint Site:

An e-mail address is by definition personal information and covered by GDPR. The e-mail addresses of project participants are stored in the ReZilient SharePoint Site. Only the project participants invited will have access. The e-mail address is a prerequisite to access the projects working area. By accepting the SharePoint invitation the participants consent to use and store their e-mail address for the purpose of online collaboration in the project.

The email addresses will be deleted when access to the project area is no longer needed (1 year after project closure).

SINTEF has signed GDPR data processing agreements with both Microsoft and the IT operations contractor handling our SharePoint platform.

7 References

European Commission. *H2020 Programme. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.0, 26 July 2016

European Commission. *Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.2, 21 March 2017

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC

List of Figures

Figure 1: Data handling procedures for ReZilient. SP=ReZilient Sharepoint..... 10